

Compassion with Clarity:
A Boundary-Compatible Compassionate Reappraisal Intervention for
Interpersonal Conflict in Hong Kong University Students

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“This thesis is my own work, and aspects where collaboration has been involved are acknowledged, and sources cited.”

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List of Abbreviations

CR: Compassion-focused reappraisal

GAD-7: Generalized Anxiety Disorder-7

PHQ-9: Patient Health Questionnaire-9

PWB: Psychological well-being

Ryff-18: Ryff Psychological Well-Being Scale, 18-item form

Abstract

Social network density and the salience of reputation concerns in university environments can blur the lines between interpersonal relationships and reputational concerns, triggering rumination, anger, and mistrust, especially in interpersonal relationships. This thesis examined Compassion with Clarity, a brief, imagery-assisted, bilingual psychoeducational intervention that helps instil compassionate reappraisal in the context of maintaining psychological boundaries. Twelve university students from Hong Kong completed screening questionnaires (PHQ-9, GAD-7) and the Ryff Psychological Well-Being Scale (18-item), as well as structured reflection worksheets linked to the intervention. A pre-post analysis of the intervention phase was conducted for all Ryff measures (quantitative), with a between-group comparison of pre-post change between the immediate and waitlist conditions, and descriptive analyses completed using worksheet coding of the primary Ryff measure. Screening scores suggested a mild-to-moderate distress profile overall (PHQ-9: $M = 9.08$, $SD = 1.98$; GAD-7: $M = 7.75$, $SD = 2.53$). Ryff total scores increased from the mean pre-intervention score ($M = 57.3$) to the mean post-intervention score ($M = 60.6$), with an average gain of 3.33 points. A paired-samples t-test indicated a positive but non-significant trend, $t(11) = -1.94$, $p = .079$, $d = -0.56$. A mixed repeated-measures ANOVA showed a similar time trend, $F(1,10) = 3.44$, $p = .093$, $\eta^2_G = .134$, but no meaningful Time \times Group interaction, $F(1,10) = 0.08$, $p = .787$. The most commonly reported coding for the worksheet questions was mixed hurt, careful disclosure, accountability before renewed trust, and slight rather than high compassion responses. Integrated analyses indicated that this intervention was related not to the forgiveness process itself, but to the recognition of hurt, clarification of boundaries, accountability, and making better next-step decisions. The findings are consistent with the conceptual logic of Compassion with Clarity and support further testing in a larger, fully powered study.

Introduction

Interpersonal conflict is a common feature of university life, as students interact in small groups and with shared circles of friendship. The effects of betrayal, gossip, and exclusion can have a significant impact on social status and emotional safety. Distress may become chronic in other ways, too, such as through rumination and repetitive negative thoughts that may arise after conflict in group work or public disclosures.

Cognitive reappraisal is a coping technique that changes the way one thinks about an event, altering its meaning and, in turn, the emotional response to the situation. In relational conflicts, it is important to distinguish between understanding the other person and forgiving the other person's actions. The line demarcating the two is even more significant for students whose social networks are more interconnected, and a healthy response may be to place limits rather than quickly return to normal levels of interaction (Ho et al., 2024; McCullough et al., 1998; Worthington, 2006).

Compassion with Clarity is a brief, imagery-assisted psychoeducational intervention designed to support moral clarity alongside compassionate reappraisal. It uses story panels with illustrations and guided practices to help participants identify their hurt, notice rumination, set limits, and make values-based choices. The intent is not to force urgent forgiveness, but to support emotional recognition and safer relational positioning.

The intervention is guided by three areas: emotion regulation, forgiveness/reconciliation, and compassionate reappraisal. Researchers and psychotherapists show that there are ways to reinterpret offences that can assist in emotional recovery processes while also helping to bring accountability and appropriate limits (Ho et al., 2024; McCullough et al., 1998; Worthington, 2006; Witvliet et al., 2010, 2011, 2015, 2022).

As can be seen in the reviewed literature, there is a practical gap: much of the reappraisal research on compassion is experimental and task-oriented, while few intervention studies are short, concise, and applicable in a private setting by students themselves. This project aims to address that by creating an intervention that is short yet balanced between still images and workbook prompts, in both English and Chinese (Mayer, 2002; Mayer & Moreno, 2003). Early stages of material piloting brought increased clarity and flow to the material and its emotional safety; additional focus during these stages was placed on the importance of compassion, accountability and emotional cues. This design choice is important as participants should not feel pressured when accessing sensitive information.

The intervention focuses on eudaimonic well-being and not just symptoms. The activity invites participants to reflect in the sense of "let's affirm our emotions, let's set limits, let's do something conscious, something oriented toward our values". Worksheets encourage participants to imagine themselves as the story character, voice their boundaries, and consider their own differences; this is aimed at strengthening the concepts of self-acceptance and communication (Ryff & Keyes, 1995).

The sequence is based on psychological studies. Using hurt terms is consistent with the idea that labelling emotions can reduce reactivity and that pain should be acknowledged before moving toward empathy (Lieberman et al., 2007; Torre & Lieberman, 2018). It is important to establish boundaries while recognising that interpersonal forgiveness does not require restored closeness, because intrapersonal forgiveness has a different focus (McCullough et al., 1998; Wade et al., 2013; Witvliet et al., 2020; Worthington, 2006). The humane-perspective step allows reflection on the "humanity of the offender," including the seriousness of the offence, and supports the next step: taking positive action consistent with personal values (Gollwitzer & Sheeran, 2006; Hayes et al., 2006; Witvliet et al., 2010; Witvliet et al., 2011; Witvliet et al., 2022).

The intervention consists of structured steps: hurt recognition, boundary clarification, humane perspective-taking, and values-aligned action. This is a progression from thinking "do I forgive?" to thinking "how do I hold what happened without abandoning myself?" It strives to convert participants from negative thinking and threat assessment toward structured reflection, labeling the hurt, establishing boundaries, maintaining accountability, and selecting a response based on values. In alignment with emotion-regulation models, this illustrates how increased eudaimonic well-being, which includes positive relationships, autonomy, and self-acceptance, could be achieved (Gross, 1998, 2015; Watkins, 2008).

This intervention is assessed through a small pilot study that includes quantitative data and structured worksheet coding, offering a process-oriented approach. This strategy helps to measure psychological changes, not just score changes—a participant may recognise hurt more clearly, rather than the intervention necessarily having misfired.

This study continues to be grounded in the original proposal, with adaptations made to accommodate the data collected to address three key questions: Does psychological well-being improve post-intervention? How large is the change between the immediate and waitlist groups? What do the worksheet answers tell us?

Importantly, the study examines the potential of compassionate reappraisal to maintain boundaries and the potential of a low-intensity, brief intervention to help students manage their relational hurts without engaging in formal therapy. If effective, this could support the development of psychoeducational supports focused on conflict-related distress, grounded in structured reflection and values-based action.

Research Questions and Hypotheses

The final thesis addresses the following questions.

RQ1. Does psychological well-being, as indexed by the Ryff-18 total score, improve from intervention-phase pre-test to intervention-phase post-test?

H1. Intervention-phase Ryff-18 total scores will show a positive pre-post trend.

RQ2. Do participants assigned to the immediate and waitlist conditions show different magnitudes of change during the intervention phase?

H2. Immediate and waitlist groups will show improvement during their intervention phase, but no big between-group difference is expected in this small pilot dataset.

RQ3. What worksheet themes characterise participants' immediate responses to the intervention, and how do those themes help interpret Ryff change?

This question is exploratory rather than hypothesis-testing. Based on the intervention logic, the expected dominant themes are hurt recognition, careful disclosure, accountability before trust, bounded compassion, and self-protective next-step action.

Methods

Design

A two-condition pilot design with repeated measures around the intervention was employed. Participants were divided into an immediate group and a waitlist group. For the final analysis, the comparison period in the intervention phase was defined as the time immediately before and after exposure to the intervention. For the immediate group, therefore, the intervention-phase pre- and post-scores corresponded to Time 1 and Time 2, respectively. The waitlist group had intervention-phase pre- and post-assessments at Times 2 and 3, respectively, because the first waitlist assessment occurred before a neutral period, and the later assessment captured the pre-to-post window after intervention exposure. This analytic structure both allowed for a descriptive comparison of intervention-phase change between groups and maximised the key question of whether well-being changed during the intervention itself.

It is important to note that no comprehensive efficacy trial was conducted with this design; it is more of a pilot and process evaluation. Pilot studies are well-suited to assess both the feasibility of recruitment and the delivery of procedures, as well as the feasibility of assessment materials and interventions (Eldridge et al., 2016; Leon et al., 2011). The experimental design further included a waitlist approach that ensured everyone received the intervention while preserving a limited comparison of the intervention-phase change. Results were presented with caution, in a non-conclusive, descriptive fashion, because the study did not include an active control group, and the sample was small (Shadish et al., 2002).

However, emotions, boundaries, compassion, and values-based action were also systematically coded and included in the interpretation of the quantitative results, as structured worksheets were included in the intervention to capture them. The overall orientation of analysis was therefore quantitative, descriptive, exploratory and process-oriented.

Participants and Recruitment

There were 12 university students in the dataset, with 6 in each condition (immediate/waitlist). A small snack incentive was provided (but unrelated to questionnaire or worksheet responses). Participants in the brief relationship-focused well-being study were recruited using the general logic presented in the

proposal—convenience-based student participation. All participants were able to read Chinese or English and complete the intervention materials within one day. The information about the participants in this dataset was provided in a coded format rather than by name. When the final analysis IDs were assigned, each ID was mapped to the older worksheet packet ID format.

Measures

Screening measures

The Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9), a brief depression symptom severity measure (Kroenke et al., 2001) and the Generalised Anxiety Disorder-7 (GAD-7), a brief measure of generalised anxiety symptoms (Spitzer et al., 2006), were used to screen for psychological distress. Conventionally, the ranges 0 to 4, 5 to 9, 10 to 14, and ≥ 15 are considered to represent minimal, mild, moderate, moderately severe to severe depression symptom levels for the PHQ-9, respectively; for the GAD-7, scores of 5, 10, and 15 correspond to mild, moderate, and severe anxiety symptom levels (Kroenke et al., 2001; Spitzer et al., 2006). Mild-to-moderate scores qualified for the study, while higher scores would be offered a bilingual safety plan with strategies to distract, trusted-person contacts, local crisis response services, campus counselling and immediate safety measures in the event they experienced emotional distress following participation. The purpose of the screening measures in the present thesis was to provide a general description of the sample's overall distress profile and to set the context for interpreting responses to the interventions.

Primary outcome measure

Psychological well-being was measured with the Ryff Psychological Well-Being Scale, 18-item form (Ryff-18). The items are evaluated on a 1 to 6 response scale, where higher scores indicate a higher level of well-being (after reverse-coding evaluative items). The reverse-coded items and six three-item subscales included self-acceptance, purpose in life, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relations and autonomy and were provided in the score sheet. The focus of this intervention analysis was on the Ryff-18 total score, given the relatively few participants and anticipated item movement, though not expected to occur across all domains at once.

There were also psychometric reasons for the decision not to interpret the brief Ryff subscales independently. Effects are unstable to interpret to be domain-specific rather than global, given the small number

of items in the 18-item form for each dimension. Additionally, prior psychometric research has found significant interdimensional commonality among the Ryff scales, suggesting that using the overall score as a descriptive measure is more suitable when the sample is small (Ryff, 2014; Springer & Hauser, 2006).

Acceptability and emotional safety items

In addition, three brief ratings were included in the questionnaire packet: helpfulness/acceptability, willingness to recommend the practice, and perceived emotional safety. These were items in the instrument set but were not the main focus herein for the present quantitative analysis.

Worksheet materials

The intervention sheets supported a process-oriented interpretation. The sheets included four questions regarding emotional responses to the Kai scenario, one inner boundary participants wished to hold, identification of reflection questions about sympathy, forgiveness and accountability, an indication of the compassion level participants felt, what they would do to keep themselves protected, a description of a personal conflict snapshot, and four follow-up questions regarding self-acceptance, compassion with clarity, next-step choice, and values-aligned action. The structure of the worksheet, therefore, provided direct evidence, at the person-by-person level, of the psychological significance associated with the pattern of quantitative change.

Intervention

Compassion with Clarity is a psychoeducational tool that uses imagery to help participants in moments of interpersonal unease, betrayal, or uncertain relational experience. The story is about a private disclosure becoming public - the prototype is a 30-minute PowerPoint. It then takes the participants through the underlying emotional reactions to that violation: replay and rumination, and then to the explicit instruction of sympathy and empathy, of compassion and of psychological boundaries. The central exercise is for the participants to keep two truths in mind at the same time: The action was wrong; the person who caused harm is still human.

Then participants are guided to name the impact of the offence, set limits, and establish a compassionate, bounded wish, while maintaining self-protection and accountability. The intervention ends with an extension of the exercise to self-acceptance, autonomy, mastery, and values-aligned action.

Procedure

Participants completed screening, Ryff measures and the intervention packet. The intervention was conducted immediately after a first assessment in the immediate condition, followed by a second Ryff assessment. The participants in the waitlist condition were assessed at the initial, a more neutral period after the first, and the post-intervention. Given that the final study materials consisted of quantitative scores and worksheets, the final analytic process took place in three phases.

First, quantitative variables related to the intervention phase were derived. The immediate participants had their pre-score at the start of the intervention and their post-score at its conclusion. The pre-score for waitlist participants was the intervention-phase score, and the post-score was the third time score. Second, the actual prompts and common response patterns were used to develop a structured codebook to index the worksheet packets. Third, data from both the quantitative and the coded qualitative data were synthesised at the individual level in an individual-level matrix to interpret the relationships among Ryff change, emotional processing, boundary choice, compassion level, and next steps.

Worksheet Coding Framework (see Appendix E)

First, a structured codebook was built through a directed content analysis and the framework method (Hsieh & Shannon, 2005; Gale et al., 2013), in which theoretically appropriate categories are established before final interpretation and remain closely linked to participants' written responses. Given that the worksheet prompts were already broken down into specific intervention processes (emotion recognition, boundary setting, compassion, accountability, and values-aligned next steps) and because there were recurring patterns in responses to these prompts, this approach was suitable (Fereday & Muir-Cochrane, 2006). For consistency, the codebook included the unit of analysis, the primary source for the worksheets, coding rules, and categorical and/or binary codes for each variable, following guidelines for clear qualitative coding and analysis using a codebook (Campbell et al., 2013). This structured codebook served as the basis for the researcher's coding of worksheet answers; therefore, the worksheet codes are single-coder descriptive classifications rather than multiple-coder ratings.

The worksheet analysis was also used as a process evaluation. In early-stage intervention research, process evidence can be used to shed light on engagement with the intervention components and whether the proposed mechanism was plausible; it can also help explain why quantitative outcomes may or may not change as

expected (Moore et al., 2015). In the present study, therefore, worksheet coding was not undertaken as an independent qualitative outcome study, but rather as a structured interpretative ancillary analysis to link the Ryff change scores to the psychological processes that were hypothesised by the intervention.

Primary emotion was coded as anger, sadness, disappointment, betrayal, confusion, or a combination of feelings (mixed hurt), based on the participant's earliest named emotion. There were three types of boundaries: distance, limit contact, and accountability before trust; not ready to talk; careful disclosure; direct communication; seek support; or mixed boundary. The level of compassion was recorded using the worksheet's own scale, and coded as none, slight, moderate and a lot. Additional binary codes tracked whether the participant explicitly recognised that the offender might have reasons or limitations, whether participants required accountability before renewed trust, and whether the participant endorsed disclosure caution (e.g., disclosing less or more selectively with private information). Finally, each participant was assigned a next-step action code, a values theme code, and a one-line process profile to summarise the dominant psychological shift in the worksheet.

The worksheet codes were not formally used as outcomes in a qualitative design. However, they were used to summarise common participant responses and to help explain what a given Ryff change score may indicate psychologically. Positive changes in the Ryff were interpreted differently when accompanied by 'accountability before trust' with slight 'compassion' as compared to high 'distance', no 'accountability' articulated.

Data Analysis

Data were analysed quantitatively using descriptive statistics, paired-samples t-tests, mixed repeated-measures ANOVA, and related figures, all of which were run in jamovi (Version 2.6; The jamovi project, 2025). The principle underpinning data analysis was the need to perform estimation, pattern-based interpretation, and process-sensitive interpretation of a small pilot dataset, in keeping with current guidance on pilot trials (Eldridge et al., 2016). For the screening data, means, standard deviations, medians and ranges were reported. The pre- and post-Ryff totals were summed, as were the intervention-phase totals. An exploratory paired-samples t-test was performed on each pair of scores to determine whether Ryff scores were higher at the end of the intervention than at the beginning for the entire sample.

The differences between immediate and waitlist on intervention-phase change were explored using a mixed repeated-measures ANOVA with Time (pre vs post) as the within-subjects factor and Group (immediate vs waitlist) as the between-subjects factor. Time \times Group interaction was the most important quantity of interest. As the number of items was small, the ANOVA was analysed descriptively, and the effect size, along with the direction of estimated marginal means, were considered alongside the p-values.

Data on worksheet coding were summarised as frequencies and percentages. A second integration check analysed the variation between selected worksheet-code categories and the Ryff change descriptively. These comparisons focused particularly on boundary type and compassion level. These descriptive analyses in groups were not analysed as confirmatory statistical tests. Their function was interpretive—to determine whether psychological stances were associated with greater, less, or more variable changes in well-being during the intervention.

Ethical Considerations

The intervention asked participants to recall or imagine interpersonal hurt experiences that may cause momentary discomfort. The study materials addressed this risk by first reinforcing that forgiveness or reconciliation was not required, second by ensuring participants chose manageable examples, and finally by helping construct a self-protective rather than self-sacrificial frame for the activity. Screening procedures also had protective properties, helping detect that distress was more or less severe. All participants were anonymised with coded IDs, and the reflection prompts expressly advised participants to use nicknames rather than personal names. The final thesis report will not contain the original identifying material – only coded, summarised, or anonymised data.

Results

Preliminary Data Profile

The final analytic sample comprised 12 participants. Screening scores indicated that the sample was neither symptom-free nor severely distressed overall. PHQ-9 totals averaged 9.08 (SD = 1.98, median = 9.00, range = 6-12), while GAD-7 totals averaged 7.75 (SD = 2.53, median = 7.00, range = 5-13). Therefore, the present sample can be described as showing a broadly mild-to-moderate distress profile overall (see Figure 1).

Figure 1

Sample screening descriptive statistics

Descriptives		
	PHQ_Total	GAD_Total
Mean	9.08	7.75
Median	9.00	7.00
Standard deviation	1.98	2.53
Minimum	6	5
Maximum	12	13

This profile aligns with the intended target population: students experiencing relational strain who may benefit from a low-intensity well-being intervention without requiring high-intensity clinical care.

Ryff-18 Descriptive Statistics

Intervention-phase Ryff totals showed a positive directional shift. Pre-intervention Ryff scores averaged 57.3 (SD = 4.97, median = 56.0), whereas post-intervention Ryff scores averaged 60.6 (SD = 4.10, median = 61.0) (see Figure 2).

Figure 2

Intervention-phase Ryff paired-samples test and descriptive statistics

Paired Samples T-Test														
		statistic	df	p	Mean difference	SE difference	95% Confidence Interval		Effect Size	95% Confidence Interval		Cohen's d	Lower	Upper
Ryff_Int_Pre	Ryff_Int_Post						Lower	Upper		Lower	Upper			
		Student's t	-1.94	11.0	.079	-3.33	1.72	-7.12	0.453	-0.559	-1.16	0.0625		

Note. $H_a: \mu_{\text{Measure 1}} - \mu_{\text{Measure 2}} \neq 0$

Descriptives					
	N	Mean	Median	SD	SE
Ryff_Int_Pre	12	57.3	56.0	4.97	1.44
Ryff_Int_Post	12	60.6	61.0	4.10	1.18

Main Pre-Post Test

A paired-samples t-test comparing intervention-phase Ryff pre- and post-total scores showed a positive but non-significant trend, $t(11) = -1.94$, $p = .079$. The mean difference was -3.33 when calculated as pre minus post, with a 95% confidence interval from -7.12 to 0.453 and Cohen's $d = -0.559$ (see Figure 2, page 13). Because the difference score was calculated as pre minus post, the negative value indicates that post-intervention Ryff scores were higher than pre-intervention scores.

Between-Group Comparison

The mixed repeated-measures ANOVA examined whether Ryff change during the intervention phase differed between the immediate and waitlist conditions. The within-subject main effect of Time approached significance, $F(1, 10) = 3.44$, $p = .093$, $\eta^2G = .134$, indicating a small-to-moderate descriptive time effect. The between-subject main effect of the Group was small and non-significant, $F(1, 10) = 1.01$, $p = .339$, $\eta^2G = .053$. Most importantly, the Time \times Group interaction was very small and non-significant, $F(1, 10) = 0.08$, $p = .787$, $\eta^2G = .003$ (see Figure 3a).

Figure 3a*Mixed repeated-measures ANOVA for intervention-phase Ryff scores*

Within Subjects Effects

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p	η^2_G
Time	66.67	1	66.67	3.4394	.093	0.134
Time * Group	1.50	1	1.50	0.0774	.787	0.003
Residual	193.83	10	19.38			

Note. Type 3 Sums of Squares

[3]

Between Subjects Effects

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p	η^2_G
Group	24.0	1	24.0	1.01	.339	0.053
Residual	237.8	10	23.8			

Note. Type 3 Sums of Squares

The estimated marginal means clarify this pattern. In Group 1, intervention-phase Ryff scores increased from 56.0 at pre-test to 59.8 at post-test. In Group 2, scores increased from 58.5 to 61.3. The two lines in the Time \times Group plot were nearly parallel, indicating that both groups improved modestly during their respective intervention phases, but not to a meaningfully different degree (see Figure 3b).

Figure 3b

Mixed repeated-measures ANOVA for intervention-phase Ryff scores

Estimated Marginal Means - Time * Group

Group	Time	Mean	SE	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower	Upper
1	Pre	56.0	2.06	51.4	60.6
	Post	59.8	1.72	56.0	63.7
2	Pre	58.5	2.06	53.9	63.1
	Post	61.3	1.72	57.5	65.2

A note of caution concerns the homogeneity of variances. Levene’s test was significant for Ryff intervention-phase pre-scores, $F(1, 10) = 5.33, p = .044$, but non-significant for post-scores, $F(1, 10) = 0.04, p = .850$ (see Figure 3c). The small sample size and the extremely modest interaction effect support a cautious descriptive interpretation rather than changing the main conclusion.

Figure 3c

Mixed repeated-measures ANOVA for intervention-phase Ryff scores

Tests of Sphericity

	Mauchly's W	p	Greenhouse-Geisser ϵ	Huynh-Feldt ϵ
Time	1.00	NaN	1.00	1.00

^a The repeated measures has only two levels. The assumption of sphericity is always met when the repeated measures has only two levels.

Homogeneity of Variances Test (Levene's)

	F	df1	df2	p
Ryff_Int_Pre	5.3327	1	10	.044
Ryff_Int_Post	0.0375	1	10	.850

Worksheet Theme Frequencies

The coded worksheet data provided a clearer, although limited, understanding of what was taking place around the score changes (see Appendix F). Betrayal, disappointment, anger, and sadness were the most frequently coded primary emotions, with mixed hurt occurring most often (50.0%) (see Figure 4a). Most participants entered the final personal reflective exercise with blended interpersonal pain.

Boundary responses were concentrated in a small set of psychologically meaningful categories. The most frequently mentioned type of boundary (41.7%) was careful disclosure, followed by accountability before trust (25.0%) and distance (25.0%). Additionally, only one participant mainly focused on direct communication (8.3%) (see Figure 4a). This implies that the intervention most often did not lead to closeness or a quick repair, but rather to better management of privacy, trust, and future contacts.

The distribution of compassion was also similar. Moderate (25.0%), slight compassion (66.7%), and no compassion (8.3%) were the most common answers. No participant reported a high or expansive level of compassion (see Figure 4a). This implies that the intervention's effect was, more often than not, limited and within a narrow range, rather than a more all-encompassing and generous change.

All 12 participants endorsed accountability, and 83.3% (N = 12) were coded as endorsing disclosure caution (see Figure 4a). For most participants, this meant that “compassion” did not involve excusing but meant instead that “compassion” went together with responsibility, prudence and restraint in future trust-building.

Figure 4a

Frequency distribution of worksheet themes

Frequencies of Primary_Emotion

Primary_Emotion	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
Anger	1.00	8.3%	8.3%
Betrayal	2.00	16.7%	25.0%
Disappointment	2.00	16.7%	41.7%
Mixed_Hurt	6.00	50.0%	91.7%
Sadness	1.00	8.3%	100.0%

Frequencies of Boundary_Type

Boundary_Type	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
Accountability_Before_Trust	3.00	25.0%	25.0%
Careful_Disclosure	5.00	41.7%	66.7%
Direct_Communication	1.00	8.3%	75.0%
Distance	3.00	25.0%	100.0%

Frequencies of Compassion_Level

Compassion_Level	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
0_None	1.00	8.3%	8.3%
1_Slight	8.00	66.7%	75.0%
2_Moderate	3.00	25.0%	100.0%

Frequencies of Accountability_Required

Accountability_Required	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
1	12.0	100.0%	100.0%

Frequencies of Disclosure_Caution

Disclosure_Caution	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
0	2.00	16.7%	16.7%
1	10.00	83.3%	100.0%

The most common next steps were to keep distance, share carefully, have a direct conversation, rebuild trust over time, protect feelings, and seek third-party help (see Figure 4b). Likewise, value themes showed a protective trend, with fairness/accountability and self-protection reported by 25.0%, and selective trust by 16.7% of participants (see Figure 4b).

Figure 4b

Frequency distribution of worksheet themes

Frequencies of Next_Step_Action

Next_Step_Action	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
Direct_Conversation	2.00	16.7%	16.7%
Distance_First	3.00	25.0%	41.7%
More_Careful_Sharing	3.00	25.0%	66.7%
Protect_Emotions	1.00	8.3%	75.0%
Rebuild_Trust_Slowly	2.00	16.7%	91.7%
Seek_Third_Party_Help	1.00	8.3%	100.0%

Frequencies of Values_Theme

Values_Theme	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
Emotional_Expression	1.00	8.3%	8.3%
Fairness_Accountability	3.00	25.0%	33.3%
Honesty	1.00	8.3%	41.7%
Privacy	1.00	8.3%	50.0%
Selective_Trust	2.00	16.7%	66.7%
Self_Protection	3.00	25.0%	91.7%
Self_Respect	1.00	8.3%	100.0%

Integration of Ryff Change and Worksheet Codes

Integration analyses were conducted descriptively to investigate differences in Ryff change across worksheet types. The following worksheet categories are based on the single-coder categories defined in Appendix E. Several patterns were observed, despite the small sample sizes.

The difference between types of boundaries was clearly described. The mean Ryff change for those who were coded as accountability before trust was +6.67 ($n = 3$), and for one person, coded as direct communication, was +7.00. The average change of the cautious disclosure group was +2.40 ($n = 5$), although it was smaller and still positive. The weakest and most variable gain was in the distance group, with an average of +0.33 ($n = 3$), ranging from -12 to +7 (see Figure 5a). These results imply that the boundaries formed by structure or contingencies are more likely to be linked to the acute effects of well-being than the distance alone.

Figure 5a

Descriptive integration of Ryff change by worksheet-coded process variables

Descriptives		
	Boundary_Type	Ryff_Change
N	Accountability_Before_Trust	3
	Careful_Disclosure	5
	Direct_Communication	1
	Distance	3
Mean	Accountability_Before_Trust	6.67
	Careful_Disclosure	2.40
	Direct_Communication	7.00
	Distance	0.333
Median	Accountability_Before_Trust	6
	Careful_Disclosure	3
	Direct_Communication	7
	Distance	6
Standard deviation	Accountability_Before_Trust	5.03
	Careful_Disclosure	2.88
	Direct_Communication	NaN
	Distance	10.7
Minimum	Accountability_Before_Trust	2
	Careful_Disclosure	-2
	Direct_Communication	7
	Distance	-12
Maximum	Accountability_Before_Trust	12
	Careful_Disclosure	6
	Direct_Communication	7
	Distance	7

The compassion variable also appeared relevant. The one participant with a no-compassion code experienced a Ryff change of -2.00. There was a greater variance among groups classified as showing slight compassion, as evidenced by an average gain of +6.13 with high average variance (+26.93; $n = 8$), compared to those coded as showing moderate compassion, as evidenced by an average change of -2.33 with high variance ($n = 3$) (see Figure 5b). Although this pattern is difficult to handle, due to the small size of the subgroups, it is in line with the goal of this intervention to elicit "bounded" compassion instead of "emotional softening" emotions.

Figure 5b

Descriptive integration of Ryff change by worksheet-coded process variables

Descriptives		
	Compassion_Level	Ryff_Change
N	0_None	1
	1_Slight	8
	2_Moderate	3
Missing	0_None	0
	1_Slight	0
	2_Moderate	0
Mean	0_None	-2.00
	1_Slight	6.13
	2_Moderate	-2.33
Median	0_None	-2
	1_Slight	6.00
	2_Moderate	2
Standard deviation	0_None	NaN
	1_Slight	3.00
	2_Moderate	8.39
Minimum	0_None	-2
	1_Slight	2
	2_Moderate	-12
Maximum	0_None	-2
	1_Slight	12
	2_Moderate	3

Ryff_Change

There was no meaningful difference in accountability because all 12 participants endorsed it. There was, however, a meaningful lack of variation around the overall positive average change, $M = 3.33$, median = 4.50, $SD = 5.96$, range = -12 to +12, with accountability always required (see Figure 5c). It seemed that the intervention did not foster the idea of turning compassion into excuse-making.

Figure 5c

Descriptive integration of Ryff change by worksheet-coded process variables

Descriptives		
	Accountability_Required	Ryff_Change
N	1	12
Missing		0
Mean		3.33
Median		4.50
Standard deviation		5.96
Minimum		-12
Maximum		12

Ryff_Change

Illustrative Participant-Level Patterns

The worksheet packets help explain the quantitative trend. Others started in anger, sadness, betrayal, or a mixture of hurt, and were later coded as clearer self-protective stances: distance, accountability, more careful disclosure, or withholding further information (see Figure 4, pages 17-18). Some people recognised that the perpetrator may have had personal problems or be humanly limited in some way, but assumed the act was hurtful and that it should not be repeated. In some packets, there arose later reflections that support “self-acceptance” (my emotions are important too; “they may have reasons, but they should take responsibility” are examples; “recalling that you did not respect values in the previous relationship, that's one reason they don't in the new one”). These patterns make the Ryff trend more interpretable: The intervention appears to encourage reorganisation of hurt rather than its relief.

Discussion

The focus of this thesis was a brief, imagery-assisted psychoeducational intervention to help students respond compassionately, without erasing boundaries, when they have been hurt in an interpersonal way. The quantitative results depicted a positive directional change in Ryff's well-being during the intervention phase, with post-intervention scores being higher than pre-intervention scores (see Figure 2, page 13). Compared to the pre-test values, the post-test values for both the paired-samples and the between-group tests were positive but non-significant, and there was no significant interaction in the Time \times Group test (see Figures 2 and 3b, page 13, 15). In summary, participants most frequently mentioned mixed hurt, careful disclosure, accountability before trust, and slight rather than strong compassion on the worksheet side (see Figure 4a, page 17). Finally, from a quantitative standpoint, increases in Ryff change were most evident if participants' worksheets indicated a level of accountability before trust or slight compassion (see Figure 5a and 5b, pages 19-20). Taken together, these results indicate that the intervention could be more effective in the moment than inducing emotional softening, and instead raise awareness of feeling hurt, remind participants of their boundaries, and help them maintain accountability and take next steps after the encounter.

Findings should be read along the same boundary-compatible reappraisal pathway outlined in the Introduction. The intervention did not explicitly aim for 'fast-forgiveness' or immediate positive emotion. Instead, it focused on the reorganisation of interpersonal hurt, from replay and confusion toward named emotion, clearer boundaries, accountability and values-aligned action. Keeping this in mind, the worksheet results are not a secondary outcome of the Ryff outcomes. They give insight into the activation of the psychological pathway. The significant consistency of the worksheet themes—mixed hurt, careful disclosure, accountability before trust, slight compassion and self-protection next steps—align with the theoretical model of the intervention. However, the quantitative change in Ryff scores was not statistically significant.

Interpretation of the Main Quantitative Pattern

The most defensible quantitative inference is that there is a positive trend in psychological well-being during the intervention phase, albeit preliminary. Data for this sample showed an increase in the total scores from a pre-intervention mean of 57.3 to a post-intervention mean of 60.6, which did not result in a conventional significant difference on a paired-samples t-test (see Figure 2 on page 13). An average increase of around three

Ryff total points may prove meaningful in a larger trial, particularly in the areas of focused change in self-acceptance, autonomy and mastery-related processes, rather than global changes, across every item. Three (on average) items showed more significant change. This is important because it implies that the intervention is not "working" as a generic emotional reset. Rather, it seems to affect specific nodes in how people perceive and respond to relationship hurt.

Compassion with Clarity is not asking people to be happier in the world within a few minutes. Rather, it has them engage in multiple mental and psychological tasks undertaken one after another: admit hurt, move rumination outside of self, articulate a boundary, respect another person's human nature without giving up the need to protect oneself, and identify an action consistent with one's values. Thus, it is not realistic to expect the same immediate and general gains across the whole population in all areas of well-being. From that perspective, the small but identifiable pre-post trend is more believable and, perhaps, more theoretically meaningful.

There was a positive trend, but the 95% confidence interval around the trend spanned 0. The interpretation should be tempered by the proposal itself, which was designed primarily for estimation and feasibility rather than for bold statements, and by the underpowered nature of these small studies. The present findings fit that guidance. They justify further development and testing, but do not justify a strong causal claim that the current intervention definitively improves eudaimonia.

Interpretation of the Between-Group Findings

The absence of a meaningful Time \times Group interaction. Both the immediate and waitlist groups showed modest improvement in their intervention periods, with an estimated marginal mean line very close to parallel (see Figure 3b, page 15). Simply, this means that the administrative condition did not alter the intervention-phase change. At a different level, it can be argued that the procedure used for implementing interventions may be relatively stable across delivery timing. After receiving the intervention, there was little difference in the mean Ryff trend between those who received it right away and those who received it later.

However, this null interaction should not be over-interpreted. The sample size was small, and pre-intervention group variances were not fully equal; the analytic objective was exploratory. The present finding of a lack of a strong differential group effect, then, should be interpreted as support for the conclusion that the present sample did not display a significant differential group effect, not as evidence that no such effect

is likely in a larger, more rigorously powered study. The absence of a group difference is still useful because it keeps the focus on the stronger signal in the present study: the common intervention-phase process across participants.

Alternative Explanations for the Non-Significant Findings

While this smaller sample size is one significant explanation, it is not the only one for the lack of statistical significance in the paired-samples test. The first concerns outcome sensitivity. The goal of the intervention was to help participants process the interpersonal hurt, particularly through hurt recognition, boundary clarification, accountability, and next steps that align with the values. The Ryff-18 total score, however, is a very general index of eudaimonic well-being. It might not be sensitive enough to detect immediate changes in more specific process areas related to rumination, unforgiveness, trust repair, boundary clarity, or state effect. This is particularly relevant for the short subscales of the Ryff as they can be unstable over small samples, and because Ryff dimensions can overlap significantly (Ryff, 2014; Springer & Hauser, 2006).

Timing is a second possibility. The post-test was given immediately after the intervention, but it may take time to consolidate the psychological target of the intervention. Participants are asked to recognise pain and consider another person's humanity, and establish self-protective boundaries in Compassion with Clarity. The steps may sometimes make painful feelings clearer at first rather than immediately alleviating distress. Hence, there may be a lagged effect that needs to be measured to determine whether boundary clarity and values-aligned behaviour later lead to greater well-being outcomes. This is consistent with the single-session intervention literature, which has noted that brief interventions can be beneficial but that outcomes can vary depending on the domain(s) of the outcome and follow-up timing (Schleider & Weisz, 2017).

A third possibility is that the intervention was intended to limit rapid emotional softening because it was boundary-compatible. The worksheet results indicated that all participants still required accountability; a majority endorsed caution in disclosure, while compassion was generally slight. Theoretically, this is a good pattern: why should the intervention be trying to achieve unconditional forgiveness/reconciliation without permitting the repetition of the behaviour? But it also implies that large overall gains aren't to be expected at this point. According to the literature on interpersonal offence, restorative elements such as offender accountability, apology, and restitution may impact the victim's empathetic and forgiving feelings. Yet, the

current intervention focused only on modifying the participants' attitude, not on offender's restitutionary actions (Witvliet et al., 2020).

Lastly, the effects of the intervention might be confounded with non-specific processes such as repeated measurement, expectancy, natural recovery, regression to the mean, and so on, which could make the waitlist design appear ineffective even if it is truly effective. Although there was a modest improvement in both groups during the intervention period, it is not possible to compare or clarify the contribution of general reflection, time and/or study participation effects, and any potential specific Compassion with Clarity effect during that period. The above limitation does not detract from the pilot findings. Still, it helps encourage a conservative reading of these findings. It reinforces the need for future research to use a larger sample, a delayed follow-up, and a more specific active control condition (Kazdin, 2007; Shadish et al., 2002).

Worksheet Themes and Their Meaning

The most interesting portion of the study is the worksheet findings. Often, participants reported feelings of hurt, betrayal, disappointment, and anger; common protective responses included careful disclosure, holding the person accountable, not restoring trust too quickly, and keeping distance. Compassion was present, though sometimes limited. This is in accordance with the intervention's design.

The project's ability to prevent misunderstanding compassion as 'letting go' or 'forgiving too soon' is a major asset. Participants highlighted the need for accountability and indicated increased concerns about further disclosures, noting the difference between learning why and agreeing to behaviour.

Themes that emerged were values associated with fairness, accountability, self-protection, and selective trust, rather than self-sacrifice and harmony. Compassionate reappraisals, then, may be considered a boundary-compatible skill that can foster compassionate cognition within the boundaries of self-respect and safety.

Why Slight Compassion May Matter Most

An intriguing pattern emerges when comparing compassion levels with shifts in the Ryff scores. Slight or low levels of compassion had the highest Ryff improvement scores compared with no compassion or moderate compassion, which had weaker and variable outcomes (see Figure 5b, page 20). This descriptive pattern suggests that slight or bounded compassion may be worth examining in future studies.

After interpersonal hurts, a slight dose of compassion might be just right, as it helps open the possibility of seeing the bigger picture and lowers hostility in the relationship while maintaining boundaries. It demonstrates an awareness of complexity and self-protection.

Moderate levels of compassion, however, do not necessarily mean improved current functioning. The ambivalent participants evinced empathy, as well as some mistrust and doubt. This means that kindness toward offenders in the early stages of post-intervention can be more psychologically complex than straightforwardly beneficial.

Boundary Type as an Index of Psychological Reorganisation

Boundary-type results clarify the likely mechanism. Gains on the Ryff scale were largest for participants who connected future trust with accountability rather than with distance only. This is important because "distance" can mean protection, unresolved withdrawal, emotional freezing, or avoidance; and "accountability before trust" means a more organised stance that allows for agency and moral clarity without pushing one into closeness.

As only one participant was in the direct-communication category, the positive outcome in this category suggests that direct communication may be beneficial when it follows a clear boundary rather than appeasement. This means there is the ability to act intentionally and in a values-appropriate way, rather than being stuck in rumination. Future studies could investigate the extent to which a series of Compassion with Clarity activities fosters a progression from identifying hurt to articulating boundaries to engage in the deliberate process of communication, and how these are related to changes in participants' well-being.

Theoretical Implications

The results indicate that compassionate reappraisal is possible alongside setting boundaries and holding another person accountable. The findings suggest that eudaimonic well-being is a relevant outcome for this intervention, as immediate changes focus on self-acceptance, emotional ownership, agency, and relationship management, not just symptom relief. Worksheets were used to guide participants in changing their perceptions of hurt, privacy, trust, and values.

This study contributes to an emerging body of knowledge about the consequences of post-offence processing as something beyond rumination versus forgiveness. In a university context, where human relationships are

highly dynamic, the intervention appears particularly well-suited in its approach to balancing emotion and honesty, moral choice and values, and self-protection and openness to understanding.

Practical Implications

The results show that a short, low-intensity intervention can be effective despite minor differences that show up immediately after treatment. This suggests that participants may have a more functional internal script, with their feelings emphasised and the steps to take next outlined. This is good for the student's well-being, since not all distressed students initially express a desire for formal counselling. Scalable support for boundary literacy, selective trust, and emotional acknowledgement can be found in a short, simple psychoeducational practice in a high-speed society.

Furthermore, this type of intervention could be used in other contexts, such as peer support, mentoring, and conflict education, without necessarily disclosing private information. The bilingual and image-assisted format makes it easier for a variety of student groups.

Limitations

Several limitations should be mentioned. First, a small sample size ($N = 12$) limited statistical testing and subgroup inference. Second, the analysis incorporated both quantitative scoring and structured worksheet coding, which enables finer-grained interpretation; although some process conclusions remain interpretive. Third, the worksheet coding followed a pre-established coding framework from the intervention, resulting in a theory-driven rather than a purely qualitative approach. Fourth, the Ryff-18 brief form total score was the main measure examined, and analyses of subscale scores would have been more stable in a larger study. Lastly, answers from this project refer only to immediate intervention-phase responses and cannot gauge whether benefits such as boundary clarity, compassion, or well-being are maintained over time.

Future Directions

Further research is needed to test the full pilot logic in the proposal, including sample size, feasibility, group comparison and acceptability (Bowen et al., 2009; Eldridge et al., 2016; Lewis et al., 2021). Adding a brief follow-up period may help determine whether immediate process changes result in lasting improvements in well-being. Furthermore, a more developed mixed-methods framework for the worksheet could contribute to modelling changes in self-acceptance, accountability, privacy management, and values-based action across

different assessments. Finally, additional research should be conducted comparing Compassion with Clarity not only with waitlists, but also with other short well-being exercises to examine the specific underlying mechanism or benefits following interpersonal hurts.

Conclusion

The design of Compassion with Clarity was guided by two goals: to help participants respond to interpersonal injuries without falling into rumination and to avoid a forced shift toward forgiveness. The results of the present study indicate a conceptual and practical promise of the intervention. Both in scores and in how participants described themselves during the intervention, there was a positive trajectory towards eudaimonic well-being. The most compelling evidence was how hurt was named, boundaries were clarified, accountability was maintained, compassion was modest and bounded, and next-step choices were made to be more intentional. The intervention, then, seems to promote a useful transition from confusion/replay mode to clearer (and safer/smoothed and more values-aligned) ways of experiencing relational hurt. The form of compassionate reappraisal that is boundary-compatible may be a significant, low-intensity intervention to support university students' well-being in a larger, more fully powered study.

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Appendices

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Appendix A

Blank PHQ-9 and GAD-7 screening questionnaire

A. PHQ-9 — Patient Health Questionnaire-9

在過去兩個星期，你有多經常受以下問題困擾？

Over the last 2 weeks, how often have you been bothered by any of the following problems?

- 0 = 完全沒有 Not at all
- 1 = 幾天 Several days
- 2 = 一半以上的天數 More than half the days
- 3 = 近乎每天 Nearly every day

- | | |
|---|-------------|
| 1. 做任何事都覺得沉悶或者根本不想做任何事
Little interest or pleasure in doing things | [0 1 2 3] |
| 2. 情緒低落、抑鬱或絕望
Feeling down, depressed, or hopeless | [0 1 2 3] |
| 3. 難於入睡；半夜會醒或相反地睡覺時間過多
Trouble falling or staying asleep, or sleeping too much | [0 1 2 3] |
| 4. 覺得疲倦或活力不足
Feeling tired or having little energy | [0 1 2 3] |
| 5. 胃口極差或進食過量
Poor appetite or overeating | [0 1 2 3] |
| 6. 不喜歡自己—覺得自己做得不好、對自己失望或有負家人期望
Feeling bad about yourself — or that you are a failure or have let yourself or your family down | [0 1 2 3] |
| 7. 難於集中精神做事，例如看報紙或看電視
Trouble concentrating on things, such as reading the newspaper or watching television | [0 1 2 3] |
| 8. 其他人反映你行動或說話遲緩；或者相反地，你比平常活動更多—坐立不安、停不下來 | [0 1 2 3] |

Moving or speaking so slowly that other people could have noticed? Or the opposite — being so fidgety or restless that you have been moving around a lot more than usual

9. 想到自己最好去死或者自殘

[0 1 2 3]

Thoughts that you would be better off dead, or of hurting yourself in some way

如果你剔選出以上任何問題,

這些問題對你的工作、處理家中事務或與人相處時來說有多少困難?

If you checked any problems, how difficult have these problems made it for you to do your work, take care of things at home, or get along with others?

- 完全沒有困難 Not difficult at all
- 有一些困難 Somewhat difficult
- 非常困難 Very difficult
- 極度困難 Extremely difficult

B. 廣泛性焦慮症量表 GAD-7 — Generalized Anxiety Disorder-7

在過去兩個星期, 你有多經常受以下問題困擾?

Over the last 2 weeks, how often have you been bothered by any of the following problems?

- 0 = 完全沒有 Not at all
- 1 = 幾天 Several days
- 2 = 一半以上的天數 More than half the days
- 3 = 近乎每天 Nearly every day

1. 感到緊張、不安或煩躁

[0 1 2 3]

Feeling nervous, anxious, or on edge

2. 無法停止或者控制憂慮

[0 1 2 3]

Not being able to stop or control worrying

3. 過分憂慮不同的事情

[0 1 2 3]

Worrying too much about different things

4. 難以放鬆 [0 1 2 3]

Trouble relaxing

5. 心緒不寧以至坐立不安 [0 1 2 3]

Being so restless that it is hard to sit still

6. 容易心煩或易怒 [0 1 2 3]

Becoming easily annoyed or irritable

7. 感到害怕, 就想要發生可怕的事情 [0 1 2 3]

Feeling afraid as if something awful might happen

如果你剔選出以上任何問題,

這些問題對你的工作、處理家中事務或與人相處時來說有多少困難?

If you checked any problems, how difficult have these problems made it for you to do your work, take care of things at home, or get along with others?

- 完全沒有困難 Not difficult at all
- 有一些困難 Somewhat difficult
- 非常困難 Very difficult
- 極度困難 Extremely difficult

Appendix B

Blank Ryff-18 and follow-up questionnaire

A. Ryff 心理幸福感量表 (18 題) Ryff Psychological Well-Being Scales (18-item)

說明: 請使用 1–6 分量表表示您的同意程度 (1 = 非常不同意, 6 = 非常同意)

Instructions: Indicate your agreement using a 1–6 scale

(1=Strongly disagree, 6=Strongly agree)

1. 我喜歡自己人格的大部分面向。 [1 2 3 4 5 6]

I like most aspects of my personality.

2. 當我回顧自己的人生故事時, 我對事情最後的發展感到滿意。 [1 2 3 4 5 6]

When I look at the story of my life, I am pleased with how things have turned out.

3. 日常生活的種種要求常讓我感到心情低落。 [1 2 3 4 5 6]

The demands of everyday life often get me down.

4. 在許多方面, 我對自己的人生成就感到失望。 [1 2 3 4 5 6]

In many ways, I feel disappointed about my achievements in life.

5. 維持親密關係對我而言一直很困難且令人挫折。 [1 2 3 4 5 6]

Maintaining close relationships has been difficult and frustrating for me.

6. 我一天一天地過日子, 並不太去想未來。 [1 2 3 4 5 6]

I live life one day at a time and do not really think about the future.

7. 總的來說, 我覺得自己能掌控所處的生活情境。 [1 2 3 4 5 6]

In general, I feel I am in charge of the situation in which I live.

8. 我很擅長處理日常生活的各項責任。 [1 2 3 4 5 6]

I am quite good at managing the responsibilities of my daily life.

9. 有時我覺得自己在生活中已經做完了所有能做的事。 [1 2 3 4 5 6]

I sometimes feel as if I've done all there is to do in life.

10. 對我而言, 人生是一個持續學習、改變與成長的過程。 [1 2 3 4 5 6]

For me, life has been a continuous process of learning, changing, and growing.

11. 我認為擁有能挑戰你對自己與世界看法的新經驗是很重要的。 [1 2 3 4 5 6]
I think it is important to have new experiences that challenge how you think about yourself and the world.
12. 別人會形容我是個樂於付出的人，願意把時間分享給他人。 [1 2 3 4 5 6]
People would describe me as a giving person, willing to share my time with others
13. 我很久以前就放棄嘗試在生活中做出重大的改善或改變了。 [1 2 3 4 5 6]
I gave up trying to make big improvements or changes in my life a long time ago.
14. 我往往會被意見強烈的人影響。 [1 2 3 4 5 6]
I tend to be influenced by people with strong opinions.
15. 我沒有經歷過太多溫暖且互信的關係。 [1 2 3 4 5 6]
I have not experienced many warm and trusting relationships with others.
16. 即使我的看法與大多數人的共識相反，我仍對自己的意見有信心。 [1 2 3 4 5 6]
I have confidence in my own opinions, even if they are contrary to the general consensus.
17. 我評價自己是依據我認為重要的事，而不是別人怎麼想。 [1 2 3 4 5 6]
I judge myself by what I think is important, not by what others think.
18. 有些人在人生中漫無目的地遊蕩，但我不是那樣的人。 [1 2 3 4 5 6]
Some people wander aimlessly through life, but I am not one of them.

B. 簡短評分 Brief Ratings

指示：請以 1-5 評分 (1 = 非常不同意, 5 = 非常同意)

1. 整體而言，這次活動對我來說是可以接受的，或對我有幫助。 [1 2 3 4 5]
Overall, this session was acceptable or helpful to me.
2. 我願意向朋友或同學推薦這次活動。 [1 2 3 4 5]
I would recommend this session to a friend or classmate.
3. 在這次活動中，我覺得情緒上是安全的。 [1 2 3 4 5]
I felt emotionally safe during this session.

Appendix C

Intervention prototype

問卷 Questionnaire

1

完成以下幸福感調查
Complete Well-Being Survey

「在開始之前，邀請你先填寫一份簡短的幸福感量表，約需五分鐘。你的回覆能幫助我們更了解：在這類經歷之後，哪些因素能支持人們的幸福感。謝謝你願意抽時間參與。」

“Before we begin, we invite you to take a short well-being questionnaire, which takes about three minutes. Your responses will help us better understand what helps support people’s well-being after experiences like these. Thank you for taking the time to participate.”

2

慈悲為本，清明自持
Compassion with Clarity

歡迎你，這是一段簡短的練習，學習安放那些我們感到些許不安的片刻。我們將探索一種不抹去界線的慈悲。此刻可稍為慢下來，你在這裡很安全。

Welcome.
This is a brief practice for moments when we feel a little insecure. We’ll explore compassion that doesn’t erase boundaries. Take a moment to slow down. You’re safe here.

3

故事片段 Story Clips 私密變公開 How it spread

Kai 在咖啡店裡向 Mina 吐露了一件私事，沒想到如今相同的細節卻在群組聊天中流傳開來—原本的私密，轉眼成了公開。

Kai confided something personal to Mina at a café. Now those same details are circulating in the group chat—what was meant to be private has suddenly become public.

4

1.1 暫停 PAUSE

如果你是Kai, 你此刻會有什麼感受?
試在紙上畫或寫下你的心情。
If you were Kai, what might you be feeling right now? Try drawing or writing it on the paper.

可能係
傷心/ 覺得被忽視/ 憤怒?
Maybe feeling sad/ ignored/
angry?

5

故事片段 Story Clips

反覆回想, 慢慢變成糾結
Replay turns into rumination

思緒開始打轉:「她為什麼要這樣做?」「是不是我太容易相信人了?」每一次反覆回想, 都讓Kai不知不覺陷得更深。

The mind starts to loop: "Why would she do this?" "Was I too trusting?" Each replay draws Kai a little deeper into the spiral.

6

故事片段 Story Clips

概念一: 安全與界線
Segment 1: Safety and Boundaries

在我們繼續Kai的故事之前, 我們先一起探討心理界線的選擇。
慈悲不等於接受傷害;
它是帶著善意、也帶著分寸地清楚看見。
今天, 如果你是Kai, 你想為自己守住哪一條界線?

Before we go further on Kai's story, let's briefly learn what are the choices of boundary. Compassion doesn't mean accepting harm. It means seeing clearly—with kindness, and with limits. If you were Kai, what boundary would you like to hold onto today?

7

1.2 暫停 PAUSE

現在把自己當作是Kai。
試在紙上寫下一條你想守住的心理界線。
If you were Kai, what's one inner boundary you'd like to hold today? Try writing it on the paper.

請先參考以下有關「心裡界線」例子!!
Please first look into the Examples below.

- ❖ 「我現在需要一點距離。」
"I need some distance right now."
- ❖ 「我會先限制接觸。」
"I'm going to limit contact."
- ❖ 「在我能再信任之前, 我需要對方承擔責任。」
"I need accountability before I can trust again."
- ❖ 「我還沒準備好談。」
"I'm not ready to talk yet."

8

▶ 故事片段 Story Clips Kai 內心的拉扯 Kai's inner conflict

「Mina 傳來一則私訊。她說那只是場意外——那晚她喝多了，因為她和男友的感情正走在破裂邊緣。她看起來很難過……卻始終沒有開口道歉。Kai 心頭一陣刺痛，卻也同時湧上一絲同情。」

“Mina sent Kai a private message. She said it was just an accident—that night she'd had too much to drink, and things with her boyfriend were already on the verge of falling apart. She seemed genuinely upset... yet she never actually apologized. Kai felt a sharp sting in his chest, and at the same time, a flicker of sympathy.”

9

▶ 故事片段 Story Clips 概念二：釐清同情·同理·慈悲·心理界線
Segment 2: Clarifying Sympathy, Empathy, Compassion and Boundaries

「慈悲不等於親近，也不為傷害找藉口；我可以祝你好，同時保護自己。」

- ❖ 讓我們輕輕釐清四個層次的關心。
- ❖ 我們往往先從同情開始—看見他人的不幸或困難，心裡一酸，替對方心疼。
- ❖ Let's gently clarify four layers of care.
- ❖ As humans, we often begin with sympathy—feeling sorry when someone is going through something hard.

10

▶ 故事片段 Story Clips 概念二：釐清同情·同理·慈悲·心理界線
Segment 2: Clarifying Sympathy, Empathy, Compassion and Boundaries

「慈悲不等於親近，也不為傷害找藉口；我可以祝你好，同時保護自己。」

- ❖ 接著是同理—更貼近地去感受，也更願意去理解對方正在經歷什麼。
- ❖ 若我們願意再往前一步，就會來到慈悲：看見痛苦，也真心祝福它能被減輕—但不把對方的痛苦背在自己身上。
- ❖ Then comes empathy—the ability to sense and understand what another person is feeling.
- ❖ If we're willing to take one more step forward, we arrive at compassion: we can see someone's suffering and sincerely wish for it to be eased—without carrying their pain as our own.

11

▶ 故事片段 Story Clips 概念二：釐清同情·同理·慈悲·心理界線
Segment 2: Clarifying Sympathy, Empathy, Compassion and Boundaries

「慈悲不等於親近，也不為傷害找藉口；我可以祝你好，同時保護自己。」

- ❖ 最後，是界線。界線會說：「我會先照顧自己，盡力保護自己。」
- ❖ 總括而言，慈悲不會為傷害找藉口，也不必意味著要靠近、要親密。
- ❖ 慈悲與心理界線可以同時存在、並行不悖。
- ❖ And then come boundaries. Boundaries gently say, “I will care for myself first, and do my best to keep myself safe.”
- ❖ In essence, compassion doesn't make excuses for harm, and it doesn't automatically mean we must draw closer or become intimate.
- ❖ Compassion and healthy psychological boundaries can exist together, side by side.

12

▶ 故事片段 Story Clips 「我是在背叛自己嗎？」
"Am I betraying myself?"

Kai 心裡反覆掙扎著一個問題：「如果我試著理解 Mina，是不是就等於背叛了自己？」可是，一味困在憤怒裡，並不會真正保護你——它只會讓你更難走出來。溫柔地看見發生了什麼，並不代表要放下自尊。

Kai wrestles with a question: "If I try to understand Mina, am I betraying myself?" But staying trapped in anger won't protect you—it only keeps you stuck. Compassion doesn't mean giving up your self-respect.

13

▶ 故事片段 Story Clips 「我是在背叛自己嗎？」
"Am I betraying myself?"

「現在，邀請你做一個小反思。你不必原諒，也不必和解。只是讓我們一起看看：在不放掉界線的前提下，你心裡是否還能留下一點點慈悲？」

"Now, a gentle reflection. You don't have to forgive. You don't have to reconcile. And still, we can explore this: is there any room for compassion—even a little—without letting go of your boundaries?"

14

2.1 暫停 PAUSE

現在把自己當作是 Kai，
試在紙上選擇兩個問題並分享你的反思。
If you were Kai, what would your reflection be?
Try to choose two questions on the paper.

1. 你是否能想到任何原因，會為 Mina 感到難過？
Is there any reason you could feel sorry for Mina?
2. Mina 需要被原諒嗎？
Does Mina need to be forgiven?
3. Mina 需要原諒自己嗎？
Does Mina need to forgive herself?
4. 你對 Mina 有任何一點難過或不捨的感覺嗎？
Do you feel sad for Mina in any way?
5. Mina 需要你的原諒嗎？
Does Mina need your forgiveness?

15

2.2 暫停 PAUSE

現在把自己當作是 Kai：你此刻能感受到多少慈悲？
同時，你想怎麼守住界線、好好保護自己？
If you were Kai, how much compassion do you feel right now?
And what boundary would help you stay safe at the same time?

試著把你的想法寫在紙上
Try writing your thoughts down on paper

例如：在分享秘密前，先想想它傳出去後會不會傷到自己。

無 (None) 少許 (A Little) 中等 (Moderate) 很多 (A Lot)

16

3.1 暫停 PAUSE 現在，為了接下來的練習，請想起一個需要你寬恕的人，為什麼是他/她呢？
只要描述一個相處摩擦的小片刻就好，可替對方取個暱稱以保護私隱。
For the next practice, bring to mind someone who needs your forgiveness, and why is him or her?
Just mention a small snapshot of the conflict, you can give them a nickname to protect privacy.

試著把你的想法寫在紙上
Try writing your thoughts down on paper

例如：小美竟然擅自刪掉我辛苦完成的小組作業部分，我真的覺得非常被冒犯。

只作參考!!!

那個片刻
The Snapshot:

17

故事片段 Story Clips 兩分鐘的引導練習
2-minute practice

我們現在要開始一段兩分鐘的引導練習。你會走過四個的小步驟，每一步之後都會有短暫的停留。準備好了嗎？

We'll now begin a two-minute guided practice. You'll move through four gentle steps, with a brief pause after each one. Are you ready?

18

故事片段 Story Clips 練習1：說出影響
Exercise 1: Name the impact

「這很痛...也正因为它很重要。」
"This hurt—and it matters."

「現在，為這份影響命名：『這很痛—也正因为它很重要。』你不需要解釋或替痛苦辯解。發生的事並不對—而且它很重要。慢慢吸一口氣，再緩緩呼出。」

"Bring the snapshot to mind. Now name the impact: 'This hurt—and it matters.' You don't need to justify the pain. What happened wasn't okay—and it matters. Take a slow breath."

19

故事片段 Story Clips 練習2：人非聖賢，過而能改
Exercise 2: Hold two truth: No one's perfect—own it and improve

「人非聖賢，過而能改」
No one's perfect—own it and improve

「現在，請在心裡想起那位造成傷害的人。試著同時握住兩個真相：他們做的事是錯的—而他們也是人。人會不完美、會受限、也可能正在掙扎；但仍需要為自己的行為負責。兩者都可以同時成立。」

"Now, bring to mind the person who caused harm. Hold two truths at once: what they did was wrong—and they are human. Human beings can be imperfect, limited, and struggling, and still be accountable. Both can be true."

20

▶ 故事片段 Story Clips 練習3: 溫柔立界線
Exercise 3: Kind but Firm Boundaries

「他們需要成長...但這件事不能再發生。」
"They need to grow... but this must not happen again."

「對方的行為背後，也許確實有原因—限制、痛苦，或是不知道該怎麼做得更好。他們可能需要成長與療癒，但這件事仍然不能再發生。你可以為他們的成長留出空間，同時也清楚地對自己說：『這不能再發生。』現在，請在心裡把這句話說一遍。」

"Their behavior may have come from something real—limits they're carrying, pain, or simply not knowing how to do better. They may need time to grow and heal, but this still must not happen again. You can make space for their growth while also drawing a clear line for yourself: 'This must not happen again.' Now, say that sentence to yourself—silently, in your mind—once."

21

▶ 故事片段 Story Clips 練習4: 慈悲有界
Exercise 4: Compassion with Boundaries

「願你學習。願你改變。願你停止造成傷害。」
May you learn. May you change. May you stop causing harm.

「在你覺得安全的距離裡，你可以送出一個簡單的祝願：『願你學習。願你改變。願你停止造成傷害。』你可以祝福對方成長，同時也為自己保留距離。」

"From a distance that feels safe for you, offer a simple wish: 'May you learn. May you change. May you stop causing harm.' You can hope for someone's growth while still keeping space for yourself."

22

3.2 暫停 PAUSE

試在紙上畫或寫下一個新想法/感覺
Try to capture one new thought/ feeling on the paper

「此刻，回想先前提到那個曾讓你感到些許不安的小片刻時，你的感受是否出現了任何變化—哪怕只有一點點？你的心裡又浮現了哪些新的想法或感受？」

"Right now, as you think back to that brief moment we mentioned earlier—the one that made you feel a little uneasy—have your feelings shifted at all, even just slightly? What new thoughts or emotions are coming up for you?"

Pause Card
新想法/感覺

例如：我真的感到非常憤怒，也無法理解小美為什麼要這麼做。我甚至不想試著去理解，就算她有她的苦衷也是一樣。她沒有主動道歉，為什麼要我去原諒她？

只作參考!!!

23

▶ 故事片段 Story Clips

要即時寬恕他人可以是一件非常困難的事，所以其實我們剛才提及過的慈悲也不等如寬恕。不過我們總有些方法和這些情緒和解，我們一同嘗試一下吧！現在，我希望能如實帶著你剛才真實情緒回答接下來的提問。Immediate forgiveness to a person can be a very difficult thing so the compassion we go through just now does not equal to forgiveness either. Despite this, we still have ways out to relieve these difficult feelings. Let's try it out together! Now, could you bring along the described emotions just now to answer the following questions on the next pages.

例如：我真的感到非常憤怒，也無法理解小美為什麼要這麼做。我甚至不想試著去理解，就算她有她的苦衷也是一樣。她沒有主動道歉，為什麼要我去原諒她？

只作參考!!!

Pause Card
新想法/感覺

24

3.3 暫停 PAUSE

現在可把空格地方當作剛才提及那人的小暱稱，試在紙上選擇兩個問題並分享你的反思。
Please fill in the empty boxes with the nickname you mentioned just now. Try to choose two questions and reflect on the paper.

1. 你是否能想到任何原因，會為 感到難過？
Is there any reason you could feel sorry for ?
2. 需要被原諒嗎？
Does need to be forgiven?
3. 需要原諒自己嗎？
Does need to forgive herself?
4. 你對 有任何一點難過或不捨的感覺嗎？
Do you feel sad for in any way?
5. 需要你的原諒嗎？
Does need your forgiveness?

25

3.4 暫停 PAUSE

你此刻能感受到多少慈悲？
同時，你想怎麼守住界線、好好保護自己？
If you were Kai, how much compassion do you feel right now?
And what boundary would help you stay safe at the same time?

試著把你的想法寫在紙上
Try writing your thoughts down on paper

例如：先與其他組員了解情況，必要時向老師反映受到不公平對待的情形。從這次經驗中吸取教訓，今後要特別留意，避免再與不負責任的同學同組。

只作參考!!!

26

故事片段 Story Clips

兩分鐘的引導練習
2-minute practice

謝謝你的投入和耐心！
我們現在要再次開始一段兩分鐘的引導練習。你會走過四個的小步驟，每一步之後都會有短暫的停留。準備好了嗎？

Thank you for your focus and patience!
We'll now begin a two-minute guided practice. You'll move through four gentle steps, with a brief pause after each one.
Are you ready?

27

4.1 暫停 PAUSE

反思1: 自我接納
Reflection 1: Self-acceptance

試著把你的想法寫在紙上
Try writing your thoughts down on paper

例如：我真的感到非常憤怒和傷心。也許她有她的原因，但我的情緒同樣重要，我不需要刻意去隱藏它。

「讓我們整合你剛才練習過的內容，先從自我接納開始：你的憤怒、你的傷痛—它們都有道理。回到你先前分享的、與那個人相關的那段不安片刻，試分享此刻你對自己的反應，多了哪些更具善意、也更理解自己的看見？」

Let's integrate what you just practiced, starting with self-acceptance: your anger and your hurt made sense. As you return to the uneasy moment you shared about that person, try sharing what kinder, more understanding insight you have now about your own reaction?

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4.2 暫停 PAUSE

反思2: 慈悲與內在清明
Reflection 2: Compassion with Clarity

試著把你的想法寫在紙上
Try writing your thoughts down on paper

「積極的關係」不代表必須在對方尚未負責的情況下，勉強自己繼續親近。你可以承認一個人的人性，同時也把自己好好保護起來。現在，試寫下一句話：一句既有慈悲，也有清楚責任與界線的話。」

“A “positive relationship” doesn’t mean you have to force closeness when the other person hasn’t taken responsibility. You can acknowledge someone’s humanity while still protecting yourself. Now, try writing one sentence—one that holds compassion, while also stating clear responsibility and boundaries.”

例如：在我能重新信任她之前，我需要她為這份傷害負起責任：真誠道歉，並願意和我坐下來，善意地溝通。

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4.3 暫停 PAUSE

反思3: 下一步的行動
Reflection 3: Next-step choice

試著把你的想法寫在紙上
Try writing your thoughts down on paper

「接下來要怎麼走，你可以自己決定。要對話？設下限制？或是拉開一點距離？你的界線由你掌握。這一週，什麼行動對你來說最合適、也最安心？」

“You get to choose what comes next. Do you want to talk, set limits, or create some distance? You’re in charge of your boundaries. What action feels right for you this week?”

例如：我會跟我信任的人或校內輔導員傾訴煩惱。因為在重新信任前，我選擇暫時退開，照顧自己；傷痛不是軟弱，而是我在乎的證明，讓我更懂得成長與守護關係。

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4.4 暫停 PAUSE

反思4: 向心而行
Reflection 4: Values-aligned “one small step”

試著把你的想法寫在紙上
Try writing your thoughts down on paper

「有沒有哪一個小步驟，能讓你更靠近自己的價值觀？也許是守住一條界線、在其他關係裡慢慢修復信任，或好好練習自我照顧。你不必急著找回完美的方向感；先踏出一小步，朝向與自己對齊的方向走就好。」

“Is there one small step you can take to move closer to your values? Maybe it’s holding a boundary, slowly rebuilding trust in other relationships, or practicing better self-care. You don’t need to rush to find a perfect sense of direction—just take one small step toward a path that feels aligned with who you are.”

例如：我嘗試在其他關係裡面修復信任，先分享無傷大雅的日常小事。

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4.5 暫停 PAUSE

試在紙上畫或寫下一個新想法/感覺
Try to capture one new thought/feeling on the paper

「此刻，回想先前提到那個曾讓你感到些許不安的小片刻時，你的感受是否出現了任何變化—哪怕只有一點點？你的心裡又浮現了哪些新的想法或感受？」

“Right now, as you think back to that brief moment we mentioned earlier—the one that made you feel a little uneasy—have your feelings shifted at all, even just slightly? What new thoughts or emotions are coming up for you?”

也許...
Maybe...

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▶ 故事片段 Story Clips

堅持練習，不求完美
Practice, not perfection

「一段時間後，Mina 主動傳來道歉。Kai 讀完後，感受到心裡的拉扯，仍選擇從清晰的地方回應：『謝謝你的道歉。我現在需要一些空間。』Kai 在心底低語：『我不必急著完美展現慈悲與內在清明；這是一段需要一步一步、持續練習的旅程。』」

"Some time later, Mina reaches out with an apology. Kai reads it, feels the inner conflict, and responds from a place of clarity: 'Thank you for apologizing. I need some space right now.' Kai murmured inwardly, 'I don't have to rush to show compassion and inner clarity perfectly—this is a journey I practice, one step at a time.'"

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完成以下幸福感調查
Complete Well-Being Survey

「你已完成這次練習。離開之前，再次邀請你填寫一份簡短的幸福度量表，大約需要三分鐘。你的回覆能幫助我們更了解：在這類經歷之後，哪些因素能支持人們的幸福。謝謝你願意抽時間參與，也謝謝你的用心投入。」

"You've completed the practice. Before you go, we invite you to fill out a brief well-being survey. It takes about three minutes. Your responses help us understand what supports well-being after experiences like these. Thank you for your time and care."

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Appendix D

Blank intervention worksheet

- 1.1 如果你是Kai, 你此刻會有什麼感受？試畫或寫下你的心情。
If you were Kai, what might you be feeling right now? Try drawing or writing it down.

例如：
可能係傷心/ 覺得被忽視/ 憤怒？
Maybe feeling sad/ ignored/ angry?

- 1.2 現在把自己當作是Kai, 試寫下一條你想守住的心理界線。
If you were Kai, what's one inner boundary you'd like to hold today? Try writing it down.

例如：
「我現在需要一點距離。」
“I need some distance right now.”
「我會先限制接觸。」
“I’m going to limit contact.”
「在我能再信任之前, 我需要對方承擔責任。」
“I need accountability before I can trust again.”
「我還沒準備好談。」
“I’m not ready to talk yet.”

2.1

現在把自己當作是Kai, 試選擇兩個問題並分享你的反思。

If you were Kai, what would your reflection be? Try to choose two questions.

題目號碼	內容

2.2

現在把自己當作是Kai: 你此刻能感受到多少慈悲?

同時, 你想怎麼守住界線、好好保護自己?

試著寫下你的想法。

If you were Kai, how much compassion do you feel right now?

And what boundary would help you stay safe at the same time?

Try writing your thoughts down.

例如:

分享秘密前, 先考慮一下這個秘密傳開後對自己的影響。

I'd be extra careful about what could happen if I shared something personal.

慈悲心程度	
Compassion level	

為了保護自己, 我會

To keep myself safe, I will

- 3.1 現在，為了接下來的練習，請想起一個需要你寬恕的人，為什麼是他/她呢？
只要描述一個相處摩擦的小片刻就好，可替對方取個暱稱以保護私隱。
試著寫下你的想法。

For the next practice, bring to mind someone who needs your forgiveness, and why is him or her?
Just mention a small snapshot of the conflict,
and you can give them a nickname to protect privacy.
Try writing your thoughts down.

例如：

小美竟然擅自刪掉我辛苦完成的小組作業部分，我真的覺得非常被冒犯。
I feel very disrespected that Mary deleted my parts of our group project.

- 3.2 試畫或寫下一個新想法/感覺
Try to capture one new thought/ feeling.

例如：

我真的感到非常憤怒，也無法理解小美為什麼要這麼做。
我甚至不想試著去理解，就算她有她的苦衷也是一樣。
她沒有主動道歉，為什麼要我去原諒她？

I feel really angry about what she did to hurt me, and I don't think I have any responsibility to understand her reasons—especially when she doesn't even feel sorry for it.

3.3

現在可把空格地方當作剛才提及那人的小暱稱，

試在紙上選擇兩個問題並分享你的反思。

Please fill in the empty boxes with the nickname you mentioned just now.

Try to choose two questions and reflect on the paper.

題目號碼	內容

3.4

你此刻能感受到多少慈悲？

同時，你想怎麼守住界線、好好保護自己？

試著寫下你的想法。

If you were Kai, how much compassion do you feel right now?

And what boundary would help you stay safe at the same time?

Try writing your thoughts down.

例如：

先與其他組員瞭解情況，有需要的話與老師報告不公平待遇。

吸收是次教訓，要特別留意，避免再次與這類不負責任的同學一組。

I'll discuss the situation with my group members to gain a better understanding of what happened and inform the teacher if necessary. This experience taught me to be more careful and avoid teaming up with irresponsible classmates next time.

慈悲心程度	
Compassion level	
為了保護自己，我會	
To keep myself safe, I will	

4.1

反思1: 自我接納

試著寫下你的想法。

Reflection 1: Self-acceptance

Try writing your thoughts down.

例如：

我真的感到非常憤怒和傷心。

也許她有她的原因，但我的情緒同樣重要，我不需要刻意去隱藏它。

I really feel angry and hurt. She might have her reasons, but my feelings matter too, and there's no need to hide these emotions.

4.2

反思2: 慈悲與內在清明

試著寫下你的想法。

Reflection 2: Compassion with Clarity

Try writing your thoughts down.

例如：

在我能重新信任她之前，我需要她為這份傷害負起責任：

真誠道歉，並願意和我坐下來，善意地溝通。

Before I can trust her again, I need her to acknowledge her wrongdoing, offer a sincere apology, and engage in a peaceful, respectful conversation with me.

4.3

反思3: 下一步的行動

試著寫下你的想法。

Reflection 3: Next-step choice

Try writing your thoughts down.

例如：

我會跟我信任的人或校內輔導員傾訴煩惱。

因為在重新信任前，我選擇暫時退開，照顧自己；

傷痛不是軟弱，而是我在乎的證明，讓我更懂得成長與守護關係。

I would express these feelings to someone I trust or to a school counselor. Before rebuilding trust with Mary, I would distance myself and prioritize self-care. Experiencing emotional pain is not a weakness but evidence that I am capable of caring deeply. This experience has taught me the importance of learning how to build and maintain healthy relationships.

4.4

反思4: 向心而行

試著寫下你的想法。

Reflection 4: Values-aligned “one small step”

Try writing your thoughts down.

例如：

我嘗試在其他人際關係中重新建立信任，先從分享一些無傷大雅的日常小事開始。

I would try to rebuild trust in other relationships, starting with simple, everyday interactions.

4.5

試畫或寫下一個新想法/感覺

Try to capture one new thought/ feeling.

Appendix E

Worksheet coding framework and codebook

This appendix describes the structured coding framework used to analyze participants' completed intervention worksheets. The framework was designed to support a quantitative, descriptive, and process-oriented interpretation of the worksheet responses while preserving consistency across all 12 participants.

Unit of analysis: one participant worksheet packet. Primary coding sources: the written responses to the emotion prompt, boundary prompt, compassion rating, reflection questions, new-thought prompt, next-step choice, and values-aligned action prompt.

A. Coding principles

- Code from what the participant explicitly wrote. Do not infer more than the text supports.
- Use the earliest relevant worksheet section for emotion and boundary coding unless a later section clearly replaces or clarifies the earlier response.
- If two emotions are equally central and neither is clearly dominant, code `Mixed_Hurt`.
- If a participant shows both understanding of the offender and insistence on responsibility, code `Offender_Has_Reasons = 1` and `Accountability_Required = 1`.
- If a participant says they will share less, protect privacy, avoid telling secrets, or be more selective in trust, code `Disclosure_Caution = 1`.
- If no single behavioral next step is dominant, code `Mixed_Action`.

B. Worksheet codebook

Variable	Type	Codes	Primary source in worksheet	Coding rule
Primary_Emotion	Nominal	Anger; Sadness; Disappointment; Betrayal; Confusion; Mixed_Hurt	1.1 and early worksheet language	Code the strongest early emotional state named by the participant. If multiple negative emotions are equally strong, code <code>Mixed_Hurt</code> .
Boundary_Type	Nominal	Distance; Limit_Contact; Accountability_Before_Trust; Not_Ready_To_Talk; Careful_Disclosure; Direct_Communication; Seek_Support; Mixed_Boundary	1.2 and later boundary-related reflections	Code the clearest protective boundary or relational limit selected by the participant.
Compassion_Level	Ordinal	0_None; 1_Slight; 2_Moderate; 3_A_Lot	2.2 or 3.4 compassion rating field	Convert the participant's own compassion rating into the ordinal code shown.
Offender_Has_Reasons	Binary	0 = No; 1 = Yes	2.1, 3.2, 4.2, 4.3	Code Yes if the participant explicitly mentions stress, problems, limitations,

				misunderstanding, or that the offender is not simply a bad person.
Accountability_Required	Binary	0 = No; 1 = Yes	1.2, 2.1, 3.3, 4.2, 4.3	Code Yes if apology, explanation, responsibility, consequence, or accountability is described as necessary before trust or repair.
Disclosure_Caution	Binary	0 = No; 1 = Yes	2.2, 3.4, 4.4, 4.5	Code Yes if the participant says they will share less, protect privacy, be more selective, or stop telling personal secrets so easily.
Next_Step_Action	Nominal	More_Careful_Sharing; Distance_First; Direct_Conversation; Observe_And_Wait; Seek_Third_Party_Help; Rebuild_Trust_Slowly; Protect_Emotions; Mixed_Action	4.3 and 4.4	Code the clearest practical step the participant says they will take after the exercise.
Values_Theme	Nominal	Self_Protection; Privacy; Honesty; Selective_Trust; Emotional_Expression; Growth_Learning; Fairness_Accountability; Self_Respect	4.1–4.4 and 4.5	Code the strongest underlying value expressed in the participant’s later reflections.
Process_Profile	Short narrative summary	Free text	Whole worksheet packet	Write a one-line analyst summary that captures the participant’s overall process, for example: hurt recognition + accountability before trust.

C. Coding decision rules for common patterns

Observed pattern	Coding decision
Participant writes “angry and disappointed” or multiple strong negative emotions	Primary_Emotion = Mixed_Hurt
Participant writes “I need some distance right now”	Boundary_Type = Distance
Participant writes “I need accountability before I can trust again”	Boundary_Type = Accountability_Before_Trust; Accountability_Required = 1
Participant says the offender may have reasons but still caused harm	Offender_Has_Reasons = 1; Accountability_Required = 1
Participant says they will tell fewer people, keep secrets, or protect privacy more carefully	Disclosure_Caution = 1; often Next_Step_Action = More_Careful_Sharing
Participant emphasizes apology, fairness, responsibility, or consequences	Values_Theme = Fairness_Accountability
Participant emphasizes protecting feelings, keeping distance, or taking care of self first	Values_Theme = Self_Protection

Appendix F
Participant-level integration appendix table

New_ID	Old_Code	Group	Ryff_Intervention_Pre	Ryff_Intervention_Post	Ryff_Change	Abs>=2_Item_Count	Primary_Emotion	Boundary_Type	Compassion_Level	Offender_Has_Reasons	Accountability_Required	Disclosure_Cautious	Next_Step_Action	Values_Theme	Process_Profile	Consolidated_Participant_Interpretation
101	101	Immediate	55	61	6	4	Mixed_Hurt	Distance	Slight	Yes	Yes	Yes	More_Careful_Sharing	Self_Protection	hurt recognition + careful privacy boundary	Began from mixed hurt and moved toward firmer protection of personal information and more selective trust. Change is best read as stronger self-protection and practical boundary-setting, rather than simple warmth toward the offender.
102	104	Immediate	56	59	3	0	Disappointment	Careful_Disclosure	Slight	Yes	Yes	Yes	More_Careful_Sharing	Selective_Trust	caution + selective trust	Showed disappointment and caution, with only slight compassion. The worksheet profile suggests careful selection of trustworthy others and clearer limits around future disclosure, even where score change was modest.
103	106	Immediate	58	60	2	9	Betrayal	Accountability_Before_Trust	Mode rate	Yes	Yes	Yes	Rebuild_Trust_Slowly	Fairness_Accountability	hurt remains + accountability before trust	A strong process case: hurt and mistrust remained real, but the participant could acknowledge the other person's humanity while still requiring responsibility before trust could be rebuilt.
104	107	Immediate	58	65	7	4	Mixed_Hurt	Distance	Slight	Yes	Yes	No	Distance_First	Self_Protection	high activation + protective distance	Responses suggested a more activated hurt state together with a clearer stance that distance and self-protection were necessary. The likely mechanism is clarification and re-grounding rather than immediate relief.
105	108	Immediate	54	52	-2	0	Disappointment	Careful_Disclosure	None	Yes	Yes	Yes	More_Careful_Sharing	Privacy	privacy-focused boundary without reconciliation	Despite low overall reactivity, the worksheet clearly pointed to protecting privacy, sharing less, and not rushing into forgiveness. Meaningful process change appeared more clearly in the written reflections than in the overall score movement.
106	110	Immediate	55	62	7	4	Anger	Direct_Communication	Slight	Yes	Yes	No	Direct_Conversation	Honesty	boundary clarity + direct communication	The participant leaned toward naming the problem directly, clarifying what was unacceptable, and communicating that limit. This profile reflects moral clarity and interpersonal structure more than emotional softening.
107	102	Waitlist	55	61	6	4	Sadness	Careful_Disclosure	Mode rate	Yes	Yes	Yes	Protect_Emotions	Emotional_Expression	sadness acknowledged + emotional protection	This profile reflects movement from sadness and shock toward protecting one's emotional state and managing what is disclosed to others. Compassion was present, but remained compatible with self-protective limits.
108	103	Waitlist	56	59	3	0	Betrayal	Accountability_Before_Trust	Mode rate	Yes	Yes	Yes	Seek_Third_Party_Help	Fairness_Accountability	betrayal + responsibility + practical support-seeking	The participant distinguished forgiveness from saying the act was acceptable, and emphasized responsibility and practical support if needed. The profile points to clearer accountability and problem-solving.
109	105	Waitlist	49	61	12	10	Mixed_Hurt	Careful_Disclosure	Slight	Yes	Yes	Yes	Rebuild_Trust_Slowly	Selective_Trust	high activation + ambivalent restructuring	One of the most psychologically active cases: strong hurt was reorganized into a more structured stance centered on safer disclosure, slower trust, and clearer conditions for any future closeness.
110	109	Waitlist	63	69	6	1	Mixed_Hurt	Accountability_Before_Trust	Slight	Yes	Yes	Yes	Distance_First	Fairness_Accountability	partial compassion + accountability + space	The reflections showed that some understanding of the offender could coexist with a strong requirement for responsibility, space, and time before trust could be considered again.
111	111	Waitlist	59	61	2	1	Mixed_Hurt	Careful_Disclosure	Slight	Yes	Yes	Yes	Direct_Conversation	Self_Respect	betrayal processed into clearer self-expression	The participant moved from feeling betrayed toward a more assertive inner stance, with clearer permission to voice feelings and decide what should remain private.
112	112	Waitlist	69	57	-12	2	Mixed_Hurt	Distance	Slight	Yes	Yes	Yes	Distance_First	Self_Protection	distance + reduced outward pull	The participant began with anger and disappointment and moved toward distance, self-protection, and reduced dependence on others' reactions. The overall pattern fits selective strengthening rather than interpersonal softening.